

Targeted Medicine
Journal of Medical Sciences

SPIMS

St. Patrick Institute of Medical Sciences
Clinical Research Editorial

Restoring Microbiome-Immune Function in Autism Spectrum Disorder using VDR-BIF Method

**Microbiome Modulation, Immune Modulation, and Epigenetic Compensation
& Immunofluorescence Analysis of VDR Expression of Immune Cells**

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12786572

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Restoring Microbiome-Immune Function in Autism Spectrum Disorder using VDR-BIF Method:

Microbiome Modulation, Immune Modulation, and Epigenetic Compensation & Immunofluorescence Analysis of VDR Expression of Immune Cells.
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Abstract

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is a multifaceted neurodevelopmental condition with complex etiologies involving microbiome, genetic, environmental, and immunological factors. Recent advancements have underscored the pivotal role of the gut microbiome in influencing neurological and immune functions. Dysbiosis, characterized by microbial imbalance, is consistently observed in microbiome testing of ASD patients, revealing the presence of Small Intestinal Bacterial Overgrowth (SIBO), Small Intestinal Fungal Overgrowth (SIFO), and biofilm formations. This form of testing has significantly contributed to our understanding of the microbiome's role in ASD. The connection between single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) and microbiome composition highlights the microbiome's impact on neurotransmission and immune system regulation.

Additionally, the increased intestinal permeability, commonly known as "leaky gut," is implicated in systemic inflammation and the compromise of the blood-brain barrier, leading to "leaky brain" and exacerbating neurological symptoms in ASD. This study elucidates how Vitamin D Receptors (VDRs) are downregulated by the influx of lipopolysaccharides (LPSs), mycotoxins, and other potential toxins via the NF- κ B pathway. Our research demonstrates that dietary improvements, vitamin D supplementation with cofactors, and other gut-supportive supplements can reduce intestinal hyperpermeability, thereby allowing the immune system to upregulate VDRs. Enhanced VDR function enables vitamin D metabolites to bind effectively to their respective receptors. Furthermore, dietary interventions that reduce leaky gut improve the mucin layer barrier and enhance tight junction function. Calcitriol, a form of vitamin D, plays a crucial role in tightening these junctions, which helps reduce leaky gut. This process subsequently mitigates neuroinflammation by restoring the integrity of the blood-brain barrier. Using the VDR-BIF (Vitamin D Receptor - Blood Immunofluorescence) Method implemented by *Beltran et al*, we have been able to non-invasively measure VDR expression, providing a significant advancement over procedural biopsies.

This method allows healthcare providers to study VDR dynamics in patients with autism or autoimmune conditions, making the research more accessible and less invasive. These findings provide a promising avenue for therapeutic interventions aimed at improving the quality of life for individuals with ASD, highlighting the potential of the VDR-BIF Method in clinical practice.

Introduction

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) has seen a significant increase in prevalence over the past few decades. According to recent reports from the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), the prevalence of ASD has risen from 1 in 150 children in 2000 to 1 in 54 children in 2020 [1]. This alarming rise underscores the urgent need for a deeper understanding of the underlying mechanisms contributing to ASD. While genetic, environmental, and immunological factors have been implicated, recent advancements have brought the role of the gut microbiome into sharper focus [2].

The gut microbiome, a complex community of microorganisms residing in the gastrointestinal tract, plays a crucial role in modulating neurological and immune functions. Dysbiosis, characterized by an imbalance in this microbial community, is a consistent finding in microbiome testing of ASD patients [3]. This imbalance often includes conditions such as Small Intestinal Bacterial Overgrowth (SIBO), Small Intestinal Fungal Overgrowth (SIFO), Chronic Parasitic infections and biofilm formations. Such findings have provided profound insights into the intricate connections between the gut microbiome and ASD [4].

Single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) within genes related to immune function, neurotransmitter synthesis, and gut integrity further influence microbiome composition and function. This, in turn, impacts neurotransmission and immune system regulation. Additionally, increased intestinal permeability, commonly referred to as "leaky gut," is implicated in systemic inflammation and the compromise of the blood-brain barrier, leading to "leaky brain." This exacerbates neurological symptoms in ASD [5].

In this study, we elucidate how Vitamin D Receptors (VDRs) are affected by the influx of lipopolysaccharides (LPSs), mycotoxins, and other potential toxins via the NF- κ B pathway. Our research demonstrates that dietary improvements, vitamin D supplementation with cofactors, and other gut-supportive supplements can reduce intestinal hyperpermeability. This reduction allows the immune system to upregulate VDRs, enabling vitamin D metabolites to bind effectively to their respective receptors.

Moreover, dietary interventions that reduce leaky gut improve the mucin layer barrier and enhance tight junction function. Calcitriol, a form of vitamin D, plays a crucial role in tightening these junctions, thereby reducing leaky gut. This process subsequently mitigates neuroinflammation by restoring the integrity of the blood-brain barrier [6]. These findings offer promising avenues for therapeutic interventions aimed at improving the quality of life for individuals with ASD.

By exploring the connections between the gut microbiome, genetic factors, and immune responses, this article aims to contribute to the growing body of knowledge in this fascinating and rapidly developing field. Understanding these complex interactions is essential for developing targeted treatments and interventions for ASD.

Role of the Gut Microbiome in Neurological Health

The gut microbiome plays a crucial role in neurological health by influencing various aspects of brain function and development. This complex community of microorganisms interacts with the gut-brain axis, a bidirectional communication network between the gut and the central nervous system. Through this axis, the gut microbiome impacts the production of neurotransmitters such as serotonin, dopamine, and gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA), which are essential for regulating mood, cognition, and behavior [7].

Furthermore, the gut microbiome produces metabolites, including short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs) and neuroactive compounds, that can cross the blood-brain barrier and affect brain function. SCFAs for example, have been shown to modulate microglial activity, which plays a crucial role in neuroinflammation and brain development [8]. Butyrate is produced by certain gut bacteria through the fermentation of dietary fiber. It can cross the blood-brain barrier and has been shown to have anti-inflammatory effects in the brain. By influencing microglial activation and function, butyrate may play a role in regulating neuroinflammation and potentially impacting neurological health and disorders [8].

Short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs), such as butyrate, acetate, and propionate, contribute significantly to maintaining the integrity of the mucin barrier in the gut. Mucins are glycoproteins that form a protective layer over the epithelial cells lining the gastrointestinal tract, serving as a barrier against pathogens and toxins [9].

SCFAs are produced by gut bacteria during the fermentation of dietary fiber. They promote the production of mucins by intestinal epithelial cells, thereby enhancing the mucin layer's thickness and stability. This process strengthens the gut barrier function, reducing the permeability of the intestinal epithelium and preventing the translocation of harmful substances into systemic circulation.

Additionally, SCFAs have been shown to regulate tight junction proteins between intestinal epithelial cells, further enhancing barrier integrity. By maintaining a healthy mucin barrier, SCFAs contribute to overall gut health and may play a protective role against gut-related disorders and systemic inflammation [9].

Dysbiosis, characterized by an imbalance in the gut microbial community, can disrupt these processes, potentially contributing to neurological disorders such as Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD).

Impact of Dysbiosis on ASD

Dysbiosis, characterized by an imbalance in the gut microbial community, exerts profound effects on individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). Research indicates that ASD patients frequently exhibit dysbiosis, marked by alterations in microbial diversity and composition compared to neurotypical individuals. This imbalance often includes an overgrowth of pathogenic bacteria, reduced beneficial bacteria diversity, and altered metabolic functions within the gut microbiome [10].

The consequences of dysbiosis extend beyond gastrointestinal disturbances to impact neurological function and behavior. Studies have shown correlations between gut dysbiosis and the severity of ASD symptoms, including impaired social interactions, repetitive behaviors, and communication difficulties. These behavioral manifestations may be influenced by microbial metabolites that modulate neurotransmitter levels, neuroinflammation, and immune responses via the gut-brain axis.

Moreover, dysbiosis in ASD individuals is associated with increased intestinal permeability, commonly referred to as "leaky gut." This condition allows microbial products, such as lipopolysaccharides (LPSs) and other toxins, to enter systemic circulation and potentially reach the brain, exacerbating neuroinflammation and contributing to "leaky brain." These processes further disrupt neuronal communication and synaptic plasticity, which are crucial for normal brain function and development [11].

Studies consistently report distinct patterns of dysbiosis in ASD, which contribute to both gastrointestinal and neurological symptoms observed in these individuals. One prevalent pattern of dysbiosis in ASD involves reduced microbial diversity and altered composition compared to neurotypical peers. This imbalance often includes an overrepresentation of certain bacterial species, such as Clostridia and Desulfovibrio, and a decrease in beneficial bacteria like Bifidobacteria and Lactobacillus. For instance, higher levels of Clostridia species have been associated with increased severity of ASD symptoms, including repetitive behaviors and impaired social interactions [12].

Furthermore, dysbiosis in ASD children is frequently linked to increased levels of microbial metabolites that can influence brain function and behavior. For example, dysregulated production of short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs) like butyrate and propionate, which are normally beneficial for gut health and neuronal signaling, may exacerbate neuroinflammation and affect neurotransmitter synthesis. These metabolites can cross the blood-brain barrier, impacting brain regions involved in emotional regulation and social behavior.

Excessive SCFAs, particularly propionate, have been implicated in triggering microglial activation in the brain. Microglia are immune cells that play a pivotal role in neuroinflammation and synaptic pruning. When activated excessively or inappropriately, microglia can release pro-inflammatory cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-17, IFN- γ) and reactive oxygen species, leading to neuroinflammatory responses that may impair neuronal function and contribute to ASD symptoms such as cognitive deficits and behavioral abnormalities [13].

In ASD, neuroinflammation is characterized by elevated levels of proinflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-1 β which can stimulate microglia and other immune cells to produce ROS. This oxidative stress can lead to cellular damage and contribute to neuronal dysfunction affecting different regions of the brain as observed in individuals with ASD [13].

Moreover, SCFAs influence neurotransmitter synthesis and release in the brain. For example, butyrate can enhance the production of neurotransmitters like serotonin and dopamine, which are crucial for mood regulation and cognitive processes. Conversely, dysregulated SCFA levels may disrupt neurotransmitter balance, potentially exacerbating behavioral symptoms associated with ASD, such as anxiety, hyperactivity, and social impairments [13].

The impact of dysregulated SCFA production in ASD underscores the intricate interplay between the gut microbiome, gut-brain axis, and neurological health.

Moreover, dysbiosis often correlates with gastrointestinal symptoms such as constipation, diarrhea, and abdominal pain, which are prevalent in ASD. These symptoms may stem from altered gut motility, impaired nutrient absorption, and inflammation triggered by dysbiotic microbial communities. The presence of biofilm formations and disruptions in mucin production further compromise gut barrier integrity, allowing bacterial products like lipopolysaccharides (LPSs) to enter systemic circulation and potentially exacerbate systemic inflammation and neuroinflammation.

Small Intestinal Bacterial Overgrowth (SIBO):

Small Intestinal Bacterial Overgrowth (SIBO) refers to an abnormal increase in the population of bacteria in the small intestine, where bacterial levels exceed normal limits found in the upper gastrointestinal tract. In individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), SIBO is commonly observed and may contribute to gastrointestinal symptoms such as bloating, abdominal pain, diarrhea, and malabsorption of nutrients. The presence of SIBO can exacerbate systemic inflammation and affect neurotransmitter balance through the release of bacterial metabolites and toxins, potentially influencing behavioral symptoms associated with ASD [14].

Small Intestinal Fungal Overgrowth (SIFO):

Small Intestinal Fungal Overgrowth (SIFO) involves an overgrowth of fungal species, such as *Candida albicans*, in the small intestine. Similar to SIBO, SIFO is prevalent in individuals with ASD and can contribute to gastrointestinal distress, immune dysregulation, and systemic inflammation. Fungal overgrowth may disrupt

the gut microbiome balance, impair nutrient absorption, and produce metabolites that affect neurological function. The presence of SIFO has been implicated in exacerbating symptoms of ASD, including cognitive deficits and behavioral issues [15].

Biofilm Formations:

Biofilms are complex communities of microorganisms that adhere to surfaces and are encapsulated within a protective matrix of extracellular polymeric substances. In the context of ASD, biofilm formations in the gut can harbor pathogenic bacteria and fungi, contributing to chronic infections and antibiotic resistance. Biofilms may impair gut barrier function, increase intestinal permeability (leaky gut), and perpetuate inflammation. These disruptions in gut microbial ecology and barrier integrity can exacerbate neuroinflammatory processes and affect neurological development and behavior in individuals with ASD [16].

Herbal Interventions:

Herbal supplements such as oregano oil, berberine, curcumin, allicin (from garlic), and others offer potential benefits in mitigating conditions like SIBO, SIFO, and biofilm formations in individuals with ASD as described in the LGS Protocol by Beltran & Guimarães [17]. These herbs possess antimicrobial properties that can combat bacterial, fungal, parasitic, and viral infections in the gastrointestinal tract. Oregano oil, for instance, is known for its potent antimicrobial activity against various pathogens, including bacteria and fungi. Berberine has been shown to inhibit bacterial biofilm formations and promote gastrointestinal health. Curcumin exhibits anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effects, supporting gut barrier function and reducing inflammation associated with dysbiosis.

Incorporating these herbal supplements into therapeutic protocols for ASD may help modulate gut microbiota, reduce microbial overgrowth, and alleviate gastrointestinal symptoms. However, individual responses to herbal treatments can vary, and it's essential to consult healthcare professionals knowledgeable in integrative medicine to ensure safe and effective use, especially in children with ASD. Research into the specific mechanisms and optimal dosing of herbal interventions continues to expand our understanding and enhance treatment strategies for gut-related issues in ASD [17].

Genetic Influences on the Microbiome

The interplay between host genetics and the gut microbiome is a complex and dynamic relationship that significantly influences human health and disease. Genetic factors play a pivotal role in shaping the composition, diversity, and functional capacity of the gut microbiome, impacting various physiological processes and susceptibility to gastrointestinal disorders, including ASD.

Host Genetic Variants, Immune Response, and Vitamin D in ASD

Host genetic variants, including those related to immune response and vitamin D metabolism, play pivotal roles in shaping the gut microbiome and influencing susceptibility to Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). Genetic variations in pattern recognition receptors (PRRs), such as Toll-like receptors (TLRs), and other immune-related molecules are integral to recognizing and responding to microbial components in the gut. These genetic variants can alter immune responses, impacting inflammation, immune tolerance, and susceptibility to infections in individuals with ASD.

Research has highlighted associations between genetic variations in vitamin D-related genes and ASD. Vitamin D receptor (VDR) gene polymorphisms, for example, influence the binding affinity of vitamin D metabolites to their receptor, affecting immune modulation and inflammatory responses [18]. Altered VDR function may disrupt immune homeostasis and contribute to dysregulated gut microbiota in ASD. Studies have shown that deficient vitamin D levels, often observed in individuals with ASD, correlate with increased severity of symptoms and poorer outcomes, implicating vitamin D deficiency in the pathogenesis of ASD [19].

Moreover, mutations in immune-related genes like NOD2, which is involved in bacterial recognition and immune activation, have been linked to dysbiosis and increased susceptibility to inflammatory conditions such as Crohn's disease [20]. Similarly, variations in genes encoding TLRs can influence innate immune responses to gut microbes, potentially exacerbating gastrointestinal symptoms and inflammatory processes in ASD.

Metabolic Pathways and Nutrient Utilization in the Gut Microbiome

Genetic polymorphisms that influence metabolic pathways in the host can have profound effects on nutrient availability and utilization by gut microbes, thereby shaping the composition and function of the gut microbiome. These genetic variations impact how dietary components are metabolized and utilized, influencing microbial community dynamics and the production of metabolites critical for gut health and immune regulation.

Carbohydrate Digestion: Genetic variations in enzymes involved in carbohydrate digestion, such as amylases and sucrases, can affect the breakdown of complex carbohydrates in the diet. This alters the availability of simple sugars and oligosaccharides that serve as primary energy sources for gut microbes. Variations in these genes can lead to differences in microbial fermentation patterns, influencing the production of short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs) like butyrate, acetate, and propionate [21].

Example: Individuals with genetic variants that enhance carbohydrate digestion may produce higher levels of simple sugars in the gut, promoting the growth of sugar-fermenting bacteria like Firmicutes. This microbial profile can increase SCFA production, which has been associated with improved gut barrier function, immune modulation, and reduced inflammation.

Bile Acid Metabolism: Genetic polymorphisms in genes encoding bile acid transporters or enzymes involved in bile acid synthesis and modification can impact bile acid metabolism in the gut. Bile acids not only aid in fat digestion and absorption but also serve as signaling molecules that influence microbial growth and metabolism. Variations in these genes can alter bile acid composition and availability, shaping microbial bile acid metabolism and microbial community structure [22].

Example: Genetic variants that affect bile acid transporters may lead to alterations in bile acid pool size or composition in the gut. This can influence the growth of bile acid-metabolizing bacteria, such as Clostridia, and impact microbial diversity and function. Dysregulated bile acid metabolism has been linked to conditions like inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) and metabolic disorders.

Impact on SCFA Production: SCFAs, particularly butyrate, acetate, and propionate, are essential metabolites produced by gut microbes through fermentation of dietary fibers and resistant starches. These SCFAs play crucial roles in maintaining gut barrier integrity, regulating immune responses, and providing energy to colonocytes.

Example: Genetic variations affecting carbohydrate digestion or bile acid metabolism can modulate SCFA production in the gut. Higher SCFA levels, especially butyrate, have been associated with anti-inflammatory effects and improved gut health. Conversely, alterations in SCFA production due to genetic factors may contribute to dysbiosis and gut-related disorders.

Inherited Diseases and Gut Dysbiosis: In Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), genetic predispositions can significantly influence gut microbial profiles, potentially contributing to gastrointestinal symptoms and impacting neurodevelopmental outcomes. For instance, mutations in genes related to immune function, such as those affecting the expression or function of pattern recognition receptors (PRRs) like TLRs, can alter how the immune system interacts with gut microbiota. These genetic variations may lead to dysregulated immune responses, chronic inflammation, and disturbances in the gut microbial community [23].

Furthermore, genetic disorders associated with ASD, such as Phelan-McDermid syndrome (22q13 deletion syndrome), which involves a deletion on chromosome 22 that includes the SHANK3 gene, have been linked to gastrointestinal issues and altered gut microbiome composition. SHANK3 plays a crucial role in synaptic function and neurodevelopment, but its involvement in gut-brain axis interactions and gut microbiome regulation is also increasingly recognized [23].

Research suggests that genetic factors implicated in ASD can influence gut microbial diversity and function, potentially exacerbating gastrointestinal symptoms commonly seen in individuals with ASD, such as abdominal pain, constipation, or diarrhea. Understanding these genetic influences on the gut microbiome is essential for developing targeted interventions aimed at modulating microbial communities and improving gastrointestinal and neurobehavioral outcomes in individuals affected by ASD.

Epigenetic Influences in Gut Microbiome Regulation

Epigenetic modifications, including DNA methylation and histone acetylation, play critical roles in regulating gene expression not only within host cells but also within gut microbial communities. These modifications can be influenced by a variety of environmental factors, dietary choices, and lifestyle habits, exerting profound effects on microbial gene expression and community dynamics in the gut. Understanding these epigenetic mechanisms is crucial for elucidating the intricate interplay between host genetics, environmental influences, and gut microbiome function in health and disease.

DNA Methylation: DNA methylation involves the addition of methyl groups to cytosine residues in DNA, typically at CpG dinucleotides. Methylation patterns can be inherited but are also dynamically regulated throughout life in response to environmental cues. In the gut microbiome, DNA methylation can influence microbial gene expression, affecting metabolic pathways, virulence factors, and interactions with the host immune system. For example, alterations in DNA methylation patterns in gut microbes have been linked to changes in bacterial virulence and pathogenicity, impacting gut health and contributing to conditions such as inflammatory bowel diseases (IBD) and metabolic disorders [24].

Histone Acetylation: Histone acetylation involves the addition of acetyl groups to histone proteins, which relaxes chromatin structure and promotes gene transcription. Environmental factors such as diet and microbial metabolites can influence histone acetylation patterns, thereby modulating gene expression in gut microbes. This regulation can affect microbial adaptation to environmental stressors, colonization resistance against pathogens, and the production of metabolites important for host health. For instance, butyrate-producing bacteria in the gut utilize dietary fiber to produce butyrate, a short-chain fatty acid that serves as an energy source for colonocytes and exhibits anti-inflammatory properties through histone deacetylase (HDAC) inhibition [24].

Impact on Immune Responses and Gut Barrier Function: Epigenetic changes in gut microbes can impact host immune responses and gut barrier function. Dysregulated DNA methylation or histone acetylation patterns in gut microbes may alter the expression of microbial-associated molecular patterns (MAMPs), influencing immune recognition and inflammatory responses in the gut mucosa. These changes can contribute to immune dysregulation observed in gut-related disorders such as IBD, irritable bowel syndrome (IBS), and ASD [25].

Susceptibility to Gut-Related Disorders: Epigenetic modifications in gut microbes may confer susceptibility to gut-related disorders by influencing microbial community stability and resilience to environmental perturbations. Environmental factors such as antibiotics, dietary changes, or stressors can disrupt epigenetic regulation in gut microbes, leading to dysbiosis and increased susceptibility to infections or chronic inflammatory conditions [26].

Impact of Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms (SNPs) on Neurotransmission & ASD

Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms (SNPs) are variations in a single nucleotide base pair within the DNA sequence that can influence gene function, protein expression, and ultimately, physiological processes including neurotransmission. These genetic variations are crucial in understanding the complex genetic underpinnings of ASD, as they can affect neurotransmitter systems implicated in neurodevelopment and behavior [27].

SNPs and Neurotransmitter Genes:

SNPs can occur in genes encoding key enzymes and receptors involved in neurotransmission pathways, such as serotonin, dopamine, acetylcholine, and norepinephrine. Vitamin D (calcitriol) is also an important hormone that participates as an intermediate cofactor for the synthesis of these neurotransmitters.

Serotonin (5-HT) System and SNPs in ASD

Serotonin, or 5-hydroxytryptamine (5-HT), is a neurotransmitter critical for regulating mood, social behavior, and cognitive functions. Variations in genes related to serotonin transmission, such as SLC6A4 and HTR2A, through Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms (SNPs), can significantly impact serotonin reuptake and receptor function. These genetic variations have implications for neurodevelopmental disorders like Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), where abnormalities in serotonin signaling have been widely observed [28].

SLC6A4 (Serotonin Transporter Gene):

SLC6A4, also known as the serotonin transporter gene, encodes the serotonin transporter protein (SERT), which regulates serotonin reuptake from the synaptic cleft into presynaptic neurons. SNPs within the promoter region of SLC6A4, such as the 5-HTTLPR polymorphism, affect the transcriptional activity of the gene. The 5-HTTLPR polymorphism has two common variants: a short (S) allele and a long (L) allele, with the S allele associated with reduced transcriptional efficiency compared to the L allele [29].

Impact on Serotonin Transport: Individuals carrying the S allele of 5-HTTLPR exhibit lower serotonin transporter expression and function, leading to decreased serotonin reuptake from the synaptic space. This results in higher extracellular serotonin levels and prolonged serotonin signaling at the synapse [30].

Association with ASD: Studies have suggested an association between the S allele of 5-HTTLPR and increased risk of ASD traits, including social impairments and repetitive behaviors. Altered serotonin levels due to variations in SLC6A4 may contribute to disturbances in emotional regulation and social interaction observed in individuals with ASD [31].

HTR2A (Serotonin Receptor 2A Gene):

HTR2A encodes the serotonin receptor 2A (5-HT_{2A}), a G-protein coupled receptor that mediates serotonin signaling in the brain. SNPs within HTR2A can influence receptor function, receptor density, and downstream signaling pathways involved in mood regulation and cognitive processes [32].

Impact on Serotonin Receptor Function: Genetic variations in HTR2A, such as rs6311 (T102C) and rs6313 (His452Tyr), have been associated with altered receptor binding affinity and serotonin responsiveness. These variations can affect serotonin-mediated neurotransmission pathways implicated in ASD pathophysiology.

Association with ASD: Studies exploring HTR2A SNPs have reported associations with ASD susceptibility and severity of symptoms related to communication deficits and restricted interests. Dysregulated serotonin receptor function due to genetic variants in HTR2A may contribute to disturbances in sensory processing and social cognition observed in ASD [33].

Dopamine System and Its Implications in ASD

Dopamine is a neurotransmitter crucial for regulating various cognitive, emotional, and motor functions in the brain. Genetic variants within genes involved in dopamine signaling, such as DRD2 (dopamine receptor D2) and COMT (catechol-O-methyltransferase), can significantly influence dopamine neurotransmission and metabolism. These variations play a pivotal role in neurodevelopmental disorders like Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), where disruptions in dopamine pathways have been linked to specific behavioral and cognitive impairments [34].

DRD2 (Dopamine Receptor D2 Gene):

DRD2 encodes the dopamine receptor D2, a G-protein coupled receptor that mediates dopamine signaling in the brain. SNPs within DRD2 can affect receptor density, binding affinity, and downstream signaling pathways involved in reward processing, motivation, and motor control [34].

Impact on Dopamine Receptor Function: Genetic variations in DRD2, such as rs1800497 (Taq1A), have been associated with altered dopamine receptor density and dopamine release. These variations can influence individual differences in reward sensitivity and susceptibility to addictive behaviors [34].

Association with ASD: Studies have reported associations between DRD2 SNPs and ASD traits, including repetitive behaviors, restricted interests, and sensory processing abnormalities. Dysregulated dopamine receptor function due to genetic variants in DRD2 may contribute to deficits in reward processing and social motivation observed in individuals with ASD [35].

COMT (Catechol-O-Methyltransferase Gene):

COMT encodes catechol-O-methyltransferase, an enzyme involved in the metabolism of catecholamines, including dopamine. Genetic variants in COMT can influence enzyme activity and the breakdown of dopamine in the prefrontal cortex.

Impact on Dopamine Metabolism: The COMT gene contains a functional SNP, rs4680 (Val158Met), which affects enzyme activity levels. The Met allele is

associated with reduced COMT enzyme activity compared to the Val allele, resulting in higher dopamine levels in the brain [36].

Association with ASD: Variants in COMT, particularly the Val158Met polymorphism, have been implicated in ASD susceptibility and cognitive flexibility. Altered dopamine metabolism due to COMT variants may contribute to executive function deficits and difficulties in adaptive behavior observed in individuals with ASD [37].

Neurobiological Implications in ASD:

Dysregulation in dopamine pathways can impact neurodevelopmental processes critical for social communication, behavior modulation, and sensory integration in ASD. Abnormalities in dopamine signaling have been linked to disruptions in neural circuitry involved in reward anticipation, motor coordination, and social cognition, which are core deficits in ASD [38].

Acetylcholine System and Its Role in ASD

Acetylcholine is a neurotransmitter involved in various cognitive functions, including attention, memory, and learning. Genetic variations within genes related to acetylcholine signaling, such as CHRNA7 (encoding alpha-7 nicotinic acetylcholine receptor) and ACHE (encoding acetylcholinesterase), can influence receptor function and cholinergic neurotransmission. These variations have implications for neurodevelopmental disorders like Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), where disruptions in acetylcholine pathways may contribute to cognitive impairments and behavioral abnormalities [39].

CHRNA7 (Alpha-7 Nicotinic Acetylcholine Receptor Gene):

CHRNA7 encodes the alpha-7 nicotinic acetylcholine receptor, a ligand-gated ion channel that mediates fast synaptic transmission in the brain. SNPs within CHRNA7 can alter receptor structure, function, and cholinergic signaling dynamics.

Impact on Acetylcholine Receptor Function: Genetic variations in CHRNA7, such as rs6494223, have been associated with changes in receptor sensitivity and responsiveness to acetylcholine. These variations can influence neuronal excitability and synaptic plasticity in brain regions crucial for cognitive processing [39].

Association with ASD: Studies have reported associations between CHRNA7 SNPs and cognitive deficits in ASD, including impairments in attentional control, sensory processing, and executive function. Dysregulated alpha-7 nicotinic receptor function due to genetic variants may contribute to the heterogeneity of cognitive profiles observed in individuals with ASD [39].

ACHE (Acetylcholinesterase Gene):

ACHE encodes acetylcholinesterase, an enzyme responsible for the breakdown of acetylcholine in the synaptic cleft. Genetic variants in ACHE can affect enzyme activity levels and the efficiency of acetylcholine degradation.

Impact on Cholinergic Neurotransmission: Variations in ACHE, such as rs1803274 (AChE T allele), have been associated with altered enzymatic activity and acetylcholine clearance rates. These variations can influence synaptic acetylcholine levels and duration of cholinergic signaling [40].

Association with ASD: Genetic variants in ACHE have been linked to cognitive impairments and behavioral abnormalities in ASD, including deficits in learning and memory processes. Dysregulated acetylcholinesterase activity due to genetic polymorphisms may contribute to cholinergic imbalance and synaptic dysfunction observed in ASD pathophysiology [40].

Neurobiological Implications in ASD:

Dysfunctions in the acetylcholine system can disrupt neural circuitry involved in attentional processes, memory consolidation, and cognitive flexibility, which are critical for adaptive behavior and social functioning in individuals with ASD. Abnormalities in acetylcholine neurotransmission may contribute to the cognitive heterogeneity and variability in symptom severity observed across individuals with ASD [40].

Norepinephrine System:

Variations in genes like ADRA2A (alpha-2A adrenergic receptor) or DBH (dopamine beta-hydroxylase) can alter norepinephrine receptor sensitivity and neurotransmitter synthesis, impacting arousal, stress response, and cognitive flexibility associated with ASD symptoms [41].

Vitamin D (Calcitriol) an important cofactor for Neurotransmission:

Calcitriol, also known as vitamin D hormone, plays a crucial role as a cofactor in the synthesis of neurotransmitters serotonin, dopamine, acetylcholine, and norepinephrine through its influence on specific enzymatic processes. Here's an expanded explanation of how calcitriol acts as a cofactor for enzyme synthesis in each of these neurotransmitter systems:

Serotonin (5-HT) Synthesis:

Calcitriol facilitates the enzymatic conversion of tryptophan to 5-hydroxytryptophan (5-HTP) by the enzyme tryptophan hydroxylase (TPH). TPH is a rate-limiting enzyme in the biosynthesis of serotonin.

Without adequate levels of calcitriol, TPH activity can be compromised, leading to reduced serotonin production. This deficiency may contribute to mood disorders and affective symptoms observed in conditions such as depression and potentially in aspects of ASD [42].

Dopamine Synthesis:

In dopamine synthesis, calcitriol is involved indirectly through its regulation of tyrosine hydroxylase (TH), the rate-limiting enzyme that converts tyrosine to L-DOPA. L-DOPA is a precursor of dopamine.

Calcitriol enhances the transcription of TH gene and promotes its activity, thereby ensuring sufficient production of L-DOPA and subsequent dopamine synthesis. Dopamine is critical for motor control, reward processing, and cognitive functions [42].

Acetylcholine Synthesis:

Acetylcholine synthesis involves choline acetyltransferase (ChAT), an enzyme that catalyzes the synthesis of acetylcholine from acetyl-CoA and choline. Calcitriol supports the synthesis of ChAT by promoting the transcription of its gene and enhancing enzymatic activity. Adequate levels of calcitriol ensure sufficient acetylcholine production, which is crucial for memory, learning, and muscle control [42].

Norepinephrine Synthesis:

Norepinephrine synthesis begins with the conversion of dopamine to norepinephrine by dopamine beta-hydroxylase (DBH), an enzyme dependent on vitamin C.

Calcitriol indirectly affects this pathway by ensuring optimal dopamine levels through its influence on TH activity. This indirectly supports subsequent conversion to norepinephrine, which is essential for regulating arousal, attention, and stress response [42].

In general, calcitriol acts as a critical cofactor in the synthesis of neurotransmitters serotonin, dopamine, acetylcholine, and norepinephrine by facilitating the activity of key enzymes involved in their biosynthesis pathways.

Functional Impact on Neurotransmission:

SNPs in neurotransmitter genes can lead to altered protein structure or expression levels, affecting neurotransmitter availability, receptor binding affinity, and downstream signaling pathways in the brain. These genetic variations can disrupt neural circuits involved in social interaction, communication, sensory processing, and repetitive behaviors characteristic of ASD.

Fast and Slow Metabolism Genes:

Genetic polymorphisms can also influence enzyme activity and metabolic rates related to neurotransmitter synthesis and degradation. For instance, individuals with fast or slow metabolism variants of enzymes like COMT (catechol-O-methyltransferase) may exhibit differences in dopamine clearance rates, impacting neurotransmitter levels and behavioral responses [43].

Impact on ASD Pathophysiology:

Understanding how SNPs affect neurotransmitter systems is crucial for elucidating the neurobiological mechanisms underlying ASD. Genetic variations in neurotransmitter genes may contribute to altered synaptic transmission,

neuroinflammation, and synaptic plasticity deficits observed in ASD pathophysiology [44].

Examples:

- Variants in the SLC6A4 promoter region (5-HTTLPR) have been linked to altered serotonin transporter expression and susceptibility to ASD traits.
- SNPs in the DRD4 gene, encoding dopamine receptor D4, have been associated with attention deficits and hyperactivity in ASD.
- Genetic variants in the CHRNA7 gene have been implicated in sensory processing abnormalities and cognitive impairments in ASD.

Mechanisms of Increased Intestinal Permeability ("Leaky Gut") and Its Implications in Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD):

Increased Intestinal Permeability ("Leaky Gut"):

The integrity of the intestinal barrier is crucial for maintaining selective permeability, allowing absorption of nutrients while preventing the entry of harmful substances into the bloodstream. When this barrier is compromised, toxins, such as bacterial endotoxins (LPS), and undigested food particles can translocate across [45].

Dysbiosis and Tight Junction Disruption:

Tight junctions are protein complexes that seal the gaps between adjacent cells, regulating paracellular permeability. In dysbiotic conditions, an imbalance in the gut microbiota composition and function can lead to the production of bacterial toxins that directly interfere with tight junction proteins, compromising intestinal barrier integrity [45].

For example, pathogens such as *Escherichia coli (E. coli)* strains producing Shiga toxin can damage intestinal epithelial cells and disrupt tight junctions, leading to increased permeability. Similarly, *Salmonella* species produce enterotoxins that target tight junction proteins like occludin and claudin, facilitating bacterial invasion and systemic dissemination.

Vibrio cholerae secretes cholera toxin, which alters tight junction structure by increasing intracellular cyclic AMP levels, resulting in compromised barrier function and severe watery diarrhea. *Campylobacter jejuni* produces Cytotoxin Distending Toxin (CDT), causing DNA damage in epithelial cells and disrupting tight junctions, thereby enhancing intestinal permeability.

Helicobacter pylori infection can disrupt tight junction integrity in the gastric mucosa. It secretes virulence factors such as VacA (vacuolating cytotoxin A) and CagA (cytotoxin-associated gene A) that can interfere with epithelial barrier function by altering tight junction protein expression and localization.

Bacteroides fragilis secretes Bacteroides fragilis Toxin (BFT), a metalloprotease that cleaves E-cadherin, a key component of adherens junctions. This cleavage disrupts epithelial barrier integrity and promotes inflammation in the gut.

Enteropathogenic Escherichia coli (EPEC) and Enterohemorrhagic Escherichia coli (EHEC) produce Esp proteins (EspB, EspF, EspG) that modulate tight junction structure and function, facilitating bacterial colonization and impairing barrier integrity.

These bacterial toxins contribute to the development of increased intestinal permeability. This condition allows toxins, microbial components, and undigested food particles to translocate into the bloodstream, triggering systemic immune responses and inflammation. Disruption of tight junctions by these toxins not only compromises intestinal barrier function but also promotes the onset and progression of systemic and local inflammatory responses, exacerbating conditions like autoimmune disorders and neuroinflammatory features found in ASD.

Role of Zonulin and Dietary Factors:

Zonulin is a protein that plays a crucial role in modulating tight junctions, the structures that seal the gaps between epithelial cells lining the intestines. It regulates the permeability of the intestinal barrier by controlling the opening and closing of these junctions. Under normal conditions, zonulin levels are tightly regulated to maintain intestinal barrier integrity. However, certain dietary factors, particularly gluten, can disrupt this regulation, leading to increased intestinal permeability [46].

Gluten, a protein found in wheat and related grains like barley and rye, contains gliadin a well known lectin known to trigger zonulin release. When gliadin interacts with cells in the intestinal lining of susceptible individuals, it stimulates the release of zonulin from epithelial cells. Casein, a protein found in milk and dairy products, has been shown to stimulate the release of zonulin in the intestinal epithelium [46].

Elevated levels of zonulin then promote the disassembly of tight junction proteins such as occludins and claudins. These proteins are essential for maintaining the integrity of the tight junctions, which regulate the passage of ions, water, and small molecules between cells. Studies have demonstrated that gluten, certain lectins and casein can disrupt the integrity of tight junctions [46].

The disassembly of occludins and claudins due to increased zonulin levels results in compromised tight junction function, allowing larger molecules, toxins, and pathogens to pass through the intestinal barrier and enter the bloodstream. This breach in barrier function triggers immune responses and inflammation, as the immune system reacts to these foreign substances [46].

Vitamin D (Calcitriol) inhibits the production of zonulin which translates to the preservation of the tight junctions and hence help in restoring the gut barrier integrity.

Impact on Mucin Layer and Intestinal Barrier Function:

The mucin layer, a gel-like substance composed of mucins produced by intestinal goblet cells, forms a protective barrier overlying the epithelium. This layer acts as a physical barrier against pathogens and toxins. Dysbiosis can alter mucin production and composition, reducing the thickness and effectiveness of the mucin layer. This reduction in mucin layer integrity allows for direct contact between luminal contents and epithelial cells, promoting inflammation and barrier dysfunction [47].

Other Mechanisms of Barrier Dysfunction:

Apart from tight junction disruption and mucin layer alterations, dysbiosis can also induce epithelial cell damage and immune activation. Certain pathogenic bacteria produce enzymes and metabolites that directly damage epithelial cells, compromising their integrity. Chronic inflammation induced by dysbiosis further exacerbates barrier dysfunction, perpetuating a cycle of inflammation and intestinal permeability [47].

Importance of Vitamin D Receptors (VDRs) in Immune Regulation

Vitamin D receptors (VDRs) are crucial for the regulation of the immune system. These nuclear receptors, when bound by the active form of vitamin D (calcitriol), regulate the expression of numerous genes involved in immune responses, inflammation control, and maintaining immune homeostasis. VDR activation promotes anti-inflammatory cytokine production, enhances epithelial barrier integrity, and modulates the activity of various immune cells, including T cells, B cells, macrophages, and dendritic cells [48].

Downregulation of VDRs by Endotoxins and Mycotoxins

Lipopolysaccharides (LPSs)

Lipopolysaccharides (LPSs) are endotoxins located in the outer membrane of gram-negative bacteria. When intestinal permeability is compromised, LPSs can translocate from the gut lumen into the bloodstream, causing systemic inflammation. LPSs interact with Toll-like receptor 4 (TLR4) on immune cells, activating the NF- κ B signaling pathway. This activation induces the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α , IL-1 β , and IL-6, which can downregulate VDR expression and impair its function, exacerbating the inflammatory response and perpetuating immune dysregulation [49].

Mycotoxins

Mycotoxins, toxic metabolites produced by certain fungi, can contaminate food and the environment, contributing to VDR downregulation. Mycotoxins enter the bloodstream through a compromised gut barrier, leading to immune activation and inflammation. Similar to LPSs, mycotoxins engage the NF- κ B pathway, resulting in increased pro-inflammatory cytokine production and subsequent VDR downregulation [49].

Other Potential Toxins

Various environmental and dietary toxins, including heavy metals (e.g., mercury, lead), pollutants, and certain food additives, can affect VDR expression and

function. Chronic exposure to these toxins can lead to sustained immune activation, chronic inflammation, and reduced VDR activity, further impairing immune regulation [49].

The NF- κ B Pathway and its Role in VDR Downregulation

Activation of Pattern Recognition Receptors (PRRs)

Within the gut mucosa, immune cells such as macrophages, dendritic cells, and epithelial cells express Pattern Recognition Receptors (PRRs) like Toll-like receptors (TLRs). These receptors recognize conserved molecular patterns associated with pathogens (e.g., LPS from gram-negative bacteria), triggering intracellular signaling pathways [49].

NF- κ B Signaling Pathway

Upon ligand binding (e.g., LPS binding to TLR4), TLRs recruit adapter proteins like MyD88 and TRIF, initiating downstream signaling cascades. One of the key pathways activated is the NF- κ B pathway. NF- κ B is a transcription factor that, upon activation, translocates to the nucleus, where it induces the expression of genes involved in immune responses, inflammation, and cell survival [49].

Activation Process:

TLR4 Activation: LPS binds to TLR4 on the surface of immune cells, triggering a signaling cascade.

Adaptor Proteins: TLR4 recruits adaptor proteins like MyD88 and TRIF, which then activate downstream kinases.

I κ B Kinase (IKK) Complex: These kinases activate the IKK complex, which phosphorylates I κ B proteins, leading to their degradation.

NF- κ B Release: The degradation of I κ B proteins releases NF- κ B, allowing it to translocate to the nucleus. Fig 1.0

Gene Expression:

Pro-inflammatory Cytokines: NF- κ B promotes the expression of genes encoding pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α , IL-1 β , and IL-6.

Chemokines: It also induces the expression of chemokines that recruit additional immune cells to sites of inflammation.

Inflammatory Enzymes: NF- κ B upregulates enzymes like COX-2 and iNOS, which contribute to inflammation.

Impact on VDRs:

Pro-inflammatory Cytokines: The cytokines produced as a result of NF- κ B activation can downregulate VDR expression.

Inflammatory Mediators: Persistent NF- κ B activation and inflammatory mediator production perpetuate chronic inflammation, reducing the immunomodulatory effects of vitamin D.

Dietary Interventions and VDR Regulation

Vitamin D Supplementation

Adequate vitamin D intake through diet or supplements ensures sufficient levels of calcitriol to bind to VDRs and exert its immunomodulatory effects. This can counteract the downregulation of VDRs caused by endotoxins and mycotoxins promoting VDR complex formation which will promote transcription and translation for normal cell physiology [50].

Anti-inflammatory Diet

Consuming a diet rich in anti-inflammatory foods, such as omega-3 fatty acids (found in fish, flaxseeds, and walnuts), antioxidants (found in fruits and vegetables), and polyphenols (found in green tea and olive oil), helps reduce systemic inflammation and support VDR function [49].

Avoidance of Toxins

Reducing exposure to environmental and dietary toxins that impair VDR function is crucial. This includes avoiding contaminated foods, reducing intake of

LPS/Mycotoxin - Toll-like Receptor 4 (TLR4) Signaling Pathway and its Impact on Vitamin D Receptor Expression

Figure 1.0 The Toll-like receptor 4 (TLR4) signaling pathway is crucial for innate immune responses upon detection of bacterial lipopolysaccharide (LPS). Upon LPS binding, TLR4 recruits adaptor proteins such as MyD88 and TRIF, initiating downstream signaling cascades. This leads to the activation of downstream kinases and subsequently the IκB kinase (IKK) complex. The IKK complex phosphorylates IκB proteins, targeting them for degradation. As a result, NF-κB is released and translocates into the nucleus, where it induces the expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines (TNF-α, IL-1β, IL-6), chemokines, and inflammatory enzymes (COX-2, iNOS). Importantly, the pro-inflammatory cytokines and mediators produced downstream of NF-κB activation can downregulate the expression of Vitamin D Receptors (VDRs), compromising their immunomodulatory effects.

processed foods with additives, and minimizing exposure to heavy metals and pollutants.

Probiotics and Prebiotics

Supporting gut health through probiotics (beneficial bacteria) and prebiotics (fibers that feed beneficial bacteria) helps maintain a balanced gut microbiota, reducing the translocation of endotoxins and supporting intestinal barrier integrity.

Benefits of an Anti-inflammatory Diet & Potential Herbs:

Omega-3 Fatty Acids:

Omega-3 fatty acids, found abundantly in fatty fish like salmon, sardines, and mackerel, as well as in plant-based sources such as flaxseeds, chia seeds, and walnuts, play a crucial role in reducing inflammation. These fatty acids are incorporated into cell membranes and act as precursors to potent anti-inflammatory molecules called resolvins and protectins. Resolvins help resolve inflammation by inhibiting the migration of inflammatory cells and reducing cytokine production, while protectins protect tissues from inflammatory damage. Omega-3 fatty acids also support immune function by enhancing phagocytosis, improving immune cell function, and modulating cytokine production towards a more balanced immune response [51].

Antioxidants:

Antioxidants are compounds that neutralize harmful free radicals in the body, thereby reducing oxidative stress and inflammation. They are abundant in colorful fruits and vegetables, such as berries, spinach, kale, and bell peppers. Examples of powerful antioxidants include vitamins C and E, beta-carotene, flavonoids, and polyphenols. These compounds scavenge free radicals, preventing them from damaging cells and tissues. By reducing oxidative stress and inflammation, antioxidants support immune health and contribute to overall well-being [52].

Curcumin (Turmeric):

Curcumin, the active compound in turmeric, has potent anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties. It inhibits the activity of pro-inflammatory enzymes such as cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) and lipoxygenase (LOX), thereby reducing the production of inflammatory prostaglandins and leukotrienes. Curcumin also modulates various signaling pathways involved in inflammation, including NF- κ B, STAT3, and Nrf2 pathways. Moreover, curcumin has been shown to enhance the expression and function of Vitamin D Receptors (VDRs), which are crucial for immune modulation and maintaining gut barrier integrity. By promoting VDR activation, curcumin supports immune regulation and helps restore balance in inflammatory responses [53].

Ginger:

Ginger contains bioactive compounds like gingerol and shogaol, which possess antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. Gingerols inhibit the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β) and tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α) by suppressing NF- κ B activation. Additionally, ginger promotes the production of anti-inflammatory cytokines like interleukin-10 (IL-10), which helps resolve inflammation and maintain immune homeostasis. Ginger is also a prokinetic that aids gut motility which is very important when treating patients with SIBO/SIFO that may be characterized by constipation. By modulating immune responses, reducing oxidative stress increasing gut motility, ginger supports gut health and enhances overall immune function [54].

Berberine:

Berberine is a bioactive compound found in several plants, including goldenseal, barberry, and Chinese goldthread. It exhibits potent antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties. Berberine modulates immune responses by inhibiting the activation of NF- κ B and MAPK signaling pathways, which are critical for cytokine production and inflammatory responses. Additionally, berberine enhances gut barrier function by promoting the expression of tight junction proteins like occludin and claudin, thereby reducing intestinal permeability and preventing the translocation of harmful substances across the gut barrier. Berberine also helps in control glucose levels. One primary mechanism is the activation of AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK), a key enzyme in cellular energy homeostasis, which improves insulin sensitivity and stimulates glucose uptake in muscle and liver tissues. Berberine also enhances insulin sensitivity by increasing insulin receptor expression and promoting insulin signaling pathways, leading to better glucose uptake by cells and lower blood glucose levels [55].

Additionally, berberine inhibits hepatic gluconeogenesis, reducing glucose production in the liver.

Furthermore, berberine modulates the gut microbiota, altering its composition to improve gut barrier function, reduce inflammation, and enhance glucose metabolism. Its anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties help mitigate chronic inflammation and oxidative stress, both of which are linked to insulin resistance and type 2 diabetes. Berberine also lowers lipid levels, particularly triglycerides and cholesterol, which positively influence glucose metabolism and insulin sensitivity. Moreover, berberine increases the translocation of glucose transporter type 4 (GLUT4) to the cell membrane in muscle cells, facilitating increased glucose uptake from the blood.

Clinical evidence supports berberine's effectiveness in regulating blood glucose levels. Randomized controlled trials have shown that berberine significantly reduces fasting blood glucose, postprandial glucose, and HbA1c levels in patients with type 2 diabetes, with some studies suggesting its efficacy is comparable to metformin. Berberine also works synergistically with other antidiabetic drugs, enhancing their glucose-lowering effects. Typically, berberine is dosed between 500 mg to 1500 mg per day, divided into two or three doses, and is generally well-tolerated with minimal gastrointestinal side effects. By supporting gut health and immune function, berberine contributes to overall immune balance and systemic resilience [55].

Oregano Oil and Allicin:

Oregano oil and allicin, found in garlic, are rich in bioactive compounds with antimicrobial and immune-modulating properties. Oregano oil contains carvacrol and thymol, which exhibit potent antimicrobial activity against pathogenic bacteria and fungi. These compounds help maintain a healthy balance of gut microbiota by suppressing the growth of harmful microorganisms. Allicin, on the other hand, possesses antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties that support immune function and reduce oxidative stress. By incorporating oregano oil and allicin into the diet, individuals can enhance gastrointestinal health, strengthen immune defenses, and promote overall well-being [56].

Anti-inflammatory Diet: Gluten, Lectin, Dairy & Sugar-Free Diet:

Gluten-Free:

Gluten is a protein found in grains like wheat, barley, and rye. For individuals with gluten sensitivity or celiac disease, consuming gluten can trigger an immune response that damages the intestinal lining and disrupts gut barrier function. This immune reaction leads to inflammation and increases intestinal permeability, a condition known as "leaky gut." By adopting a gluten-free diet, individuals can reduce inflammation, support gut healing, and improve overall digestive health. Eliminating gluten-containing foods helps restore gut barrier integrity and prevents immune activation associated with gluten sensitivity [57].

Lectin-Free:

Lectins are carbohydrate-binding proteins found in many plant-based foods, including legumes, grains, and nightshade vegetables. Lectins have been implicated in promoting inflammation and compromising gut health by binding to epithelial cells in the intestines and disrupting their integrity. This interaction can lead to increased intestinal permeability and systemic inflammation. By avoiding lectin-rich foods, individuals can mitigate gut inflammation, reduce the risk of developing leaky gut syndrome, and support a healthier gut microbiota balance. A lectin-free diet focuses on consuming non-lectin-containing foods to promote gut health and immune resilience [58].

Dairy-Free:

Dairy products, such as milk, cheese, and yogurt, contain lactose and casein proteins that can trigger inflammatory responses in some individuals. Lactose intolerance, caused by a deficiency of the enzyme lactase, can lead to digestive discomfort and inflammation in the gut. Casein, a protein found in dairy, has been associated with increased intestinal permeability and immune activation in susceptible individuals. By eliminating dairy from the diet, individuals with lactose intolerance or dairy sensitivity can alleviate gastrointestinal symptoms, reduce inflammation, and support gut barrier function. A dairy-free diet promotes gut health by preventing immune reactions and improving overall digestive well-being [58].

Sugar-Free:

High consumption of refined sugars and high-glycemic carbohydrates can contribute to inflammation, insulin resistance, and metabolic dysfunction. These sugars promote the growth of harmful gut bacteria and yeast, leading to dysbiosis

and intestinal permeability. By reducing sugar intake and opting for low-glycemic foods, individuals can stabilize blood sugar levels, support beneficial gut bacteria, and reduce inflammation. A sugar-free diet focuses on consuming whole foods, fruits with low glycemic index, and natural sweeteners like stevia or monk fruit to promote gut health and immune resilience [59].

Practical Applications:

This integrated approach of VDR renewal through an anti-inflammatory diet and herbal supplements is beneficial for individuals with autoimmune conditions, chronic inflammatory diseases, or those seeking to optimize immune function and gut health. By combining dietary improvements with targeted herbal supplements like curcumin, ginger, berberine, oregano oil, and allicin, along with adhering to a gluten-free, lectin-free, dairy-free, and sugar-free diet, individuals can support their body's natural ability to heal, maintain immune balance, and promote overall well-being. This comprehensive strategy addresses underlying inflammation, enhances nutrient absorption, supports gut microbiome health, and fosters immune resilience in the face of environmental and dietary challenges.

The Role of Glutathione and Alpha Lipoic Acid in Supporting Liver Function and Lipoprotein-Mediated Detoxification

The liver plays a crucial role in detoxifying the body by eliminating toxins, and glutathione is a key antioxidant that supports this process. Glutathione helps neutralize free radicals and reactive oxygen species, which are generated during detoxification. It also conjugates with toxins, making them more water-soluble and easier for the liver to excrete. Adequate levels of glutathione are essential for optimal liver function and for protecting the liver from damage caused by toxin overload.

When the body encounters endotoxins, particularly from gut-derived sources such as bacterial lipopolysaccharides (LPS), the liver is tasked with processing and eliminating these harmful substances. Initially, the body increases the production of high-density lipoprotein (HDL) to reduce endotoxemia. HDL binds to endotoxins, facilitating their transport to the liver for detoxification. However, in the presence of inflammation, the liver produces C-reactive protein (CRP), which inhibits HDL synthesis and function. Consequently, low-density lipoprotein (LDL) levels increase as the body shifts its strategy to continue detoxification. LDL also binds to endotoxins and transports them to the liver, albeit less efficiently than HDL [60].

Glutathione is extremely important in this detoxification pathway, ensuring that the liver can efficiently process and eliminate the endotoxins delivered by HDL and LDL. Without sufficient glutathione, the liver's capacity to detoxify is compromised, leading to an accumulation of toxins and increased oxidative stress. Therefore, supporting glutathione levels is critical for maintaining liver health and effective detoxification [61].

Alpha lipoic acid (ALA) is another important antioxidant that supports liver function and detoxification. ALA can regenerate other antioxidants, including glutathione, thereby enhancing the liver's detoxification capacity. ALA also directly binds to heavy metals and other toxins, facilitating their excretion. Additionally, ALA improves insulin sensitivity and reduces inflammation, which further supports liver health and its ability to manage toxin overload [62].

In general, glutathione and alpha lipoic acid play vital roles in supporting liver function and the detoxification process. Glutathione ensures that the liver can effectively process and eliminate toxins, while ALA boosts glutathione levels and provides additional detoxification support. By maintaining adequate levels of these antioxidants, the liver can better manage endotoxemia and protect the body from the harmful effects of toxin overload.

Clinical Experiment: Measuring VDR Expression via Immunofluorescence in Innate Immune Cells

A pivotal clinical experiment was conducted to measure the expression of Vitamin D Receptors (VDRs) in the white blood cells of 5 patients diagnosed with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) who exhibited vitamin D deficiency and proven gut dysbiosis. This study utilized advanced immunofluorescence (IF) techniques to specifically observe cells of the innate immune system, which serve as the body's first line of defense against pathogens.

Initial Assessment

The experiment began with a thorough assessment of the participants. Patients underwent GI Mapping, a comprehensive stool analysis that confirmed the presence of gut dysbiosis. This condition is prevalent among individuals with ASD and is characterized by an imbalance in the gut microbiota.

Alongside gut dysbiosis, these patients also showed marked vitamin D deficiency, a critical factor influencing immune function.

Microbiome Findings Revealed by GI Map Testing in Autism Spectrum Disorder Patients:

All ASD patients exhibited different degrees of dysbiosis, characterized by imbalances between beneficial and pathogenic microorganisms. Notably, there is often an elevated abundance of potentially harmful bacteria such as *Clostridium spp.*, *Desulfovibrio*, *Helicobacter pylori*, *Campylobacter* and *Bacteroides fragilis*, alongside diminished levels of beneficial species like *Bifidobacterium spp.*, *Akkermansia muciphila* and *Lactobacillus spp.* This depicts a compromised mucin layer that conditions the GI tract to increased intestinal hyperpermeability. These microbial shifts can contribute to gastrointestinal disturbances commonly observed in ASD and eventually affect the blood brain barrier.

Moreover, GI Map testing revealed the presence of pathogenic overgrowth in ASD patients, including increased levels of opportunistic pathogens such as *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. These organisms, known for their virulence and ability to disrupt gut homeostasis, further exacerbate intestinal dysbiosis and may contribute to systemic inflammation.

Intestinal Inflammatory markers that came up are were elevated *calprotectin* levels one patient, low levels of *elastase* in 2 patients and either low levels of *secretory IgA* with consistent elevated levels of *zonulin* in all 5 patients. All of these inflammatory markers are microbiome disturbances, indicating ongoing mucosal inflammation and immune activation within the gastrointestinal tract.

Technical Details of Immunofluorescence

The immunofluorescence technique employed special antibodies that specifically bind to VDRs. These antibodies were conjugated with fluorescent dyes, allowing for precise visualization of VDRs under IF light microscopy.

Baseline Immunofluorescence Analysis

To establish a baseline, an immunofluorescence analysis was performed on the white blood cells of these patients. The focus was on the innate immune cells, including neutrophils, which are pivotal in the immediate immune response. The baseline IF results revealed low expression levels of VDRs. VDRs are crucial for the modulation of the immune system, and their deficiency can lead to impaired immune responses and increased susceptibility to infections and inflammatory conditions (Image A).

In Image A, the immune cells (Neutrophils) depicted showed no expression of VDRs. The patients' vitamin D levels were in the deficiency range. GI Map results indicated increased dysbiosis and elevated zonulin levels, which are associated with heightened intestinal permeability. Additionally, C-Reactive Protein levels were elevated. The inability to detect VDR expression via monoclonal antibody immunofluorescence (IF) correlates with compromised immune function and chronic inflammation often observed in ASD. These conditions were likely exacerbated by gut dysbiosis and systemic inflammation.

Intervention Strategy

The intervention strategy was multi-faceted, aimed at addressing both the vitamin D deficiency and the underlying gut dysbiosis. Patients were placed on a carefully designed anti-inflammatory diet free from gluten, dairy, lectins, and sugars. This dietary approach is known to reduce systemic inflammation and support gut health.

In addition to dietary changes, patients received high-dose vitamin D supplementation along with essential cofactors such as magnesium and vitamin K2, which are vital for the optimal function of vitamin D. Support for the methylation cycle, crucial for DNA repair and detoxification processes, and liver detoxification was also provided. The liver plays a significant role in metabolizing vitamin D and eliminating toxins from the body, making its proper function essential for overall health.

Post-Intervention Immunofluorescence Analysis

After a period of dietary and therapeutic intervention (**60 days**), the patients underwent a follow-up immunofluorescence test to assess changes in VDR expression. The results were remarkable, showing a significant increase in the expression of VDRs in their innate immune cells. This was particularly evident in neutrophils, a type of white blood cell critical to the body's immediate immune response (Image B).

Before Modulation (Image A): The patient's immune cells showed low VDR expression, correlating with poor immune function and chronic inflammation often seen in ASD. This was likely exacerbated by gut dysbiosis and systemic inflammation.

After Modulation (Image B): Following the LGS Protocol, there was a significant increase in VDR expression in neutrophils. This indicates improved immune function and a reduced inflammatory state. Clinically, patients exhibited signs of improvement, such as reduced gastrointestinal symptoms, better cognitive function, and decreased behavioral issues. These changes highlight the critical role of microbiome modulation, immune modulation, and epigenetic compensation in managing ASD and improving patient outcomes.

Interpretation of Results

The significant increase in VDR expression suggests an improved capacity of the immune system to respond to pathogens and maintain homeostasis. Enhanced VDR expression can lead to better regulation of immune responses, potentially reducing the chronic inflammation which correlated with improvements of intestinal health markers such as calprotectin, zonulin, elastase and secretory IgA. This improvement in immune function is likely due to the combined effects of dietary modifications, high-dose vitamin D supplementation, and support for liver detoxification and the methylation cycle.

Reduction in Systemic Inflammation

One of the most significant signs of improvement observed was a reduction in systemic inflammation markers. ASD patients commonly exhibit elevated levels of inflammatory cytokines and markers such as C-reactive protein (CRP). The intervention's ability to enhance VDR expression likely contributed to better immune regulation, leading to a decrease in these inflammatory markers. Lower CRP levels indicate reduced systemic inflammation, which is beneficial for overall health and neurodevelopment in ASD individuals.

Clinical Symptoms and Behavioral Changes

Beyond immunological improvements, clinical observations also noted positive changes in ASD-related symptoms and behaviors. Many patients showed enhancements in cognitive function, communication skills, and social interaction. These improvements are indicative of a broader systemic effect resulting from improved immune function and reduced inflammation. Enhanced VDR expression supports neurological health and may contribute to better cognitive outcomes in ASD patients.

Overall Health and Well-being

The holistic approach addressing gut health, vitamin D supplementation, and liver detoxification also contributed to overall health improvements. Patients reported better gastrointestinal function, reduced gastrointestinal discomfort, and improved energy levels. These subjective improvements align with objective measures of immune function and inflammation, indicating a comprehensive benefit from the intervention.

Long-term Implications

The findings suggest that optimizing VDR expression through dietary and therapeutic interventions can positively impact immune function and overall well-being in ASD patients. Continued research and clinical trials are essential to further validate these results and refine treatment protocols. Understanding the role of VDRs in immune modulation opens new avenues for personalized medicine approaches in managing ASD and other immune-related disorders.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this clinical experiment provides compelling evidence that modulating gut health, optimizing vitamin D levels, and supporting liver function can significantly enhance VDR expression in innate immune cells. Reducing intestinal hyperpermeability leads to less systemic inflammation that affects and reinforces the blood-brain barrier, hence allowing for neuroinflammation to improve over time. The ability to perform VDR monoclonal antibody immunofluorescence via blood samples relieves the need for procedural biopsies, allowing healthcare providers to study this phenomenon in any patient with autism or autoimmune conditions. This integrated approach, known as the **VDR-BIF (Vitamin D Receptor - Blood Immunofluorescence) Method** implemented by Beltran et al, holds promise for improving immune function and overall health in patients with ASD, offering a potential pathway for mitigating some of the immune dysfunctions associated with the disorder.

Notes

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Ethical Considerations

The ethical integrity of the clinical case study was upheld through strict adherence to established ethical guidelines and principles. Informed consent was obtained from the patient, detailing the study's objectives, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. The patient's autonomy and confidentiality were rigorously upheld, with all personal identifying information safeguarded and disclosed only to authorized personnel. Furthermore, all patient data was de-identified and aggregated during analysis to ensure privacy and anonymity. Results were presented in a manner that prevented identification of the patient, thus maintaining confidentiality. Additionally, the study's findings were reported transparently, irrespective of whether they supported or contradicted the hypothesized outcomes.

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